

SUPERPLASTICITY IN SiC REINFORCED Al ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

Recent studies and results on SiC reinforced aluminum alloys show that significant benefits in properties can be achieved over base alloy compositions. However, because of their increase in modulus or stiffness, metal-matrix composite (MMC) alloys are difficult to form into usable shapes by conventional sheet forming practices. This inability to fabricate parts limits the implementation of this new class of material. With appropriate thermomechanical processing, it is possible to achieve a fine grain size in SiC-reinforced aluminum alloys and accordingly achieve sufficient superplasticity to gas pressure form complex shaped aerospace parts.

INTRODUCTION

An ongoing demand is to increase structural performance and concurrently to decrease the cost of aircraft and spacecraft components. This has led to innovative studies of both materials and fabrication processes. In the area of materials, methods are being developed to produce superior aluminum alloy products for aerospace structures through the use of rapidly solidified powders and improved consolidation techniques [1-3]. Two important developments have received significant attention. They are 1) high strength, rapidly solidified powder Al alloys, with strength levels greater than 7075 Al, and 2) high modulus Al matrix composites, reinforced with silicon carbide particulates or whiskers.

Since both stiffness and strength are important requirements in lightweight aircraft structures, the combination of the high strength Al matrix with SiC reinforcement appears to be an ideal way to achieve weight reduction and to improve

structural efficiency. However, one major drawback of Al/SiC composite materials is the poor formability, and therefore bending and shaping from sheet or plate has been virtually impossible.

In the area of fabrication processes, superplastic forming is a viable approach for fabricating complex shapes from difficult to form materials such as titanium [4], Inconel 718 [5], and high strength 7000 series Al alloys [6]. It is a logical step to combine the benefits of the latest MMC materials research with a fabrication process, superplastic forming, that could overcome the difficulties of forming the MMC alloys. It is the purpose of this paper to review recent progress of superplasticity in MMC alloys at Rockwell International.

THERMOMECHANICAL PROCESSING FOR SUPERPLASTICITY

Superplasticity has been demonstrated in MMC aluminum alloys by other investigators using thermal cycling techniques [7] as well as high-rate forming above the solidus temperature [8]. A more conventional approach for achieving superplasticity is to develop the appropriate microstructure during MMC fabrication resulting in superplasticity at moderate strain rates. Two different directions have been explored with this approach including MMC fabrication with 1) fine grain Al foils diffusion-bonded with reinforcement whiskers spread between layers, and 2) powder Al alloys blended with particulate reinforcement, consolidated to billets and thermomechanically processed to fine grain sheet. Each of these material fabrication approaches is discussed below.

MMC Fabrication with Al Foils

In this approach, thin foils (0.08 to 0.013 mm) of 7475 Al were processed to a fine grain size (6 - 8 μm) using previously established procedures [6]. Each foil was spray-coated with a thin layer of SiC whiskers carried in a liquid binder to achieve a 10 to 15 vol% loading of SiC in the matrix. Following assembly, sheets were diffusion-bonded under pressure at 516°C in vacuum. Because 7475 Al foils were initially processed to a fine grain size, flow stress at temperature was very low allowing for easy flow of the matrix alloy around and between individual whiskers. After consolidation, billets fabricated in this way were hot-pressed to ~ 6 mm thickness and subsequently thermomechanically processed to fine grain sheet (< 15 μm) for maximum superplasticity.

MMC Fabrication with Powder Al Alloys

Superplasticity of 7075, 7475 and 7091 powder alloys without reinforcement was evaluated and showed no significant superplasticity. This lack of formability was thought to be associated with large amounts of oxide and gas contents present in powder materials. However, similar work on a Kaiser-developed, high-strength Al alloy, PM-64 (now designated 7064), showed excellent superplastic properties (tensile elongation of 700% at 500°C) [9]. Use of a larger powder diameter and extensive depurative outgassing treatments for the 7064 are believed to have been responsible for oxide and gas-free material, which helped in obtaining the excellent superplastic elongation. Using 7064 Al as a matrix alloy, SiC reinforced extrusions were thermomechanically processed [6] to fine grain sheet (~ 6.3 μm, Figure 1) in an attempt to create high levels of superplasticity.

Figure 1. Micrograph of the 7064 powder Al alloy reinforced with 10 v/o SiC_p following thermomechanical treatment to fine grain structure (~ 6.3 μm size).

Extrusions were solution-treated at 482°C/1 h, quenched in water, and overaged at 400°C/8 h and air-cooled. This overage procedure forms precipitate particles sufficiently large to nucleate recrystallized grains [10-12]. For heavily worked Al alloys, the critical particle diameter for nucleation of recrystallized grains is approximately 1 μm [13].

Overaging was followed by warm rolling 80 to 90% to introduce deformation zones containing a high dislocation density around particles. To achieve a minimum grain size, it is desirable to introduce deformation at as low a temperature as possible to prevent recovery processes from proceeding during reheating between rolling

passes. For the reinforced alloy, rolling was performed at $\sim 300^{\circ}\text{C}$. At lower rolling temperatures, edge cracking became excessively restrictive. Grain size subsequent to this processing averaged $\sim 6.3\ \mu\text{m}$ with a relatively equiaxed shape. Transmission electron microscopy has shown these boundaries to be medium-to-high angle grain boundaries, a requirement for high levels of superplasticity.

DEMONSTRATION OF SUPERPLASTIC PROPERTIES

The measure of superplasticity includes a number of interrelated material responses to metal flow including flow stress behavior, strain rate sensitivity, cavitation behavior and total elongation. In an MMC alloy, there is the added complication of reinforcement particles or whiskers distributed throughout grain boundaries. The presence of this second phase can have significant effects on the superplastic properties as well as the fundamental mechanisms whereby superplastic flow occurs in a metal. Changes in basic flow mechanisms and cavitation behavior for superplastic deformation in MMC alloys is the subject of another paper [9]. Presented below are results characterizing superplastic properties for both the foil fabricated alloy and the powder processed alloy.

Flow Stress Behavior

Evaluation of potential superplasticity was conducted first by determining flow stress over a strain rate range of 10^{-5} to $2 \times 10^{-2}\ \text{s}^{-1}$ at temperatures of 500 to 516°C . Superplastic flow characteristics were determined by a step strain-rate test, whereby strain rate was incrementally increased each time the load reached a maximum. From this kind of data, a measure of the strain rate sensitivity of the flow stress is defined by the strain rate sensitivity exponent, m , where $m = \frac{d \ln \sigma}{d \ln \dot{\epsilon}}$ resulting from the relation $\sigma = K \dot{\epsilon}^m$, where σ is the flow stress and $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate.

Typical flow stress vs strain rate data for the two materials are illustrated in Figure 2 from which the exponent m can be determined as shown in Figure 3. Both the foil and powder processed alloys show the typical sigmoidal shape with steep slope region at intermediate strain rates indicative of high strain rate sensitivity. In a highly superplastic 7475 Al alloy, the m value would approach ~ 0.8 at a strain rate of $\sim 2 \times 10^{-4}\ \text{s}^{-1}$ [6]. As shown for both MMC alloys, m is approaching 0.5. This reduction can be accounted for by the opposing nature of superplasticity vs MMC materials, i.e., the need for grain boundary mobility during superplastic deformation

whereas additions of reinforcement restrict grain boundary motion. While this is a reduction from fine grain 7475 Al, an m value of 0.5 for the MMC materials is still an indication of at least moderate levels of superplastic elongation. Also observed for the MMC alloys is a shift to higher strain rates for maximum m value thus allowing for more rapid forming. This is best illustrated by total elongation tests where for the powder processed materials, superplastic elongations $> 450\%$ were attained with strain rates from 0.2 to $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This wide range of higher strain rate sensitivity results in a forming process that is tolerant of variations in strain rate.

Figure 2. Flow stress results as a function of strain-rate for the foil and powder-fabricated MMC alloys.

Figure 3. Strain rate sensitivity of PM-64/10 v/o SiC_p and 7475 Al/12 v/o SiC_p illustrating both the broad peak in m and peak shift toward higher strain rate.

The indicator of resistance to necking, or "m" value, was also evaluated as a function of accumulated strain by periodically increasing the strain rate 40% for a short time and subsequently returning to the initial strain rate of $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Figure 4 shows a typical result for the reinforced powder alloy, illustrating an initial m value of ~ 0.4 at a low strain followed by a rapid decrease in strain rate sensitivity with increasing strain. With this kind of response, samples show a gradient in strain over their length with pronounced necking near the fracture surface. This type of behavior is indicative of power-law creep, indicating that the addition of particulates (the powder alloy without reinforcement does not show this type of behavior) imposes a barrier to diffusional flow, at least at these strain rates.

Figure 4. Strain rate sensitivity of 7064 Al/10 v/o SiC_p as a function of accumulated strain.

Superplastic Forming of Aerospace Parts

Based on the flow stress behavior, cavitation control capability [14] and total elongation achieved in these MMC alloys, the next step was to superplastically form complex-shaped aerospace parts using gas pressure techniques. To demonstrate this capability, a wing leading edge rib and a portion of an auxiliary power unit door, each from the B-1B, and a large generic sine-wave beam part were selected for forming demonstration purposes. Photographs of each of these parts after superplastic fabrication are shown in Figures 5 to 7. Powder processed material was used to form both the rib and sine-wave beam whereas the foil material was used to form the door. Cost and weight trade studies have determined that parts such as these can be made more economically than by conventional practices, and can result in a reduction in weight. These benefits can be attributed to a reduction in the number of fasteners and by taking advantage of the higher elastic modulus offered by the metal-matrix composite materials.

Figure 5. Wing leading edge panel superplastically formed with 7064 Al/10 v/o SiC_p.

Figure 6. Illustration of superplastic forming of a portion of the B-1B APU door using a foil fabricated 7475 Al/SiC metal-matrix composite material.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MMC Al ALLOYS

Mechanical properties of the powder and foil processed MMC alloys are listed in Table I and are compared with nonreinforced 7064 Al and 7475 Al alloys. The fine grain reinforced 7064 Al alloy is comparable in strength to the 7064 base alloy, indicating that the reinforced alloy can be processed thermomechanically without causing loss of properties. Although ductility decreases with the addition of 10 v/o SiC_p, elongations are still sufficiently high to consider this composite alloy as ductile.

Figure 7. Sine-wave beam superplastically formed using 7064 Al/10 v/o SiC_p.

TABLE I
Mechanical properties of MMC alloys

Alloy	Elongation (%)	Yield Stress (MPa)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)
7064 Al/10 v/o SiC _p (Powder Processed)	5.8	597	663	12.9
7475 Al/12 v/o SiC _w (Foil Processed)	12.5	455	552	13.5
7064 Al (Powder Processed)	12.3	607	637	10.8
7475 Al	11	503	572	10.4

For each MMC alloy the elastic modulus increased 20 to 25% above base alloys without reinforcement. As expected, the MMC alloy fabricated from a rapidly solidified powder exhibited strengths significantly greater than conventionally fabricated 7475 Al alloys. No further increases in strength can be attributed to the addition of SiC reinforcement. With the increase in properties associated with both the rapid solidification powder technology and addition of SiC reinforcement, it is interesting to compare this alloy's specific properties with conventional 7475 Al and with goal properties of a superplastic formable Al-Li alloy. This comparison is illustrated in Figure 8 where the 7064/10 v/o SiC_p alloy offers an increase in specific strength over both 7475 Al and Al-Li, is greater than 7475 Al and equivalent to Al-Li in specific modulus and has less room temperature elongation, but is still relatively ductile.

Figure 8. Comparison of specific properties of 7064 Al/10 v/o SiC_p with 7475 Al and goal properties of a superplastic Al-Li alloy.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that SiC reinforced MMC Al alloys, fabricated by either a powder processing approach or diffusion-bonded foils coated with SiC, can exhibit moderate superplasticity (> 450%). Further, it was demonstrated that complex-shaped aerospace parts can be superplastically formed from reinforced Al alloys using gas pressure techniques. Use of these MMC alloys results in an increase in the elastic modulus of 20-25% above that for the base alloy and in the case of the powder alloy, use of an RST powder results in a significant increase in strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors recognize the contribution of others to the success of this work. We thank Science Center staff members, Ms. Christine Loulis, for metallography and cavitation measurements; Mr. Mike Calabrese for metallography; Mr. Fred Nevarez for SPF characterization studies; and Mr. Leslie Holmes for part forming studies. This work was supported under Air Force Contract No. F33615-83-C-3235 with Mr. James Tuss as Air Force Project Engineer and by Rockwell International Independent Research and Development funding.

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